

IMPACT OF THE AVAILABILITY OF QUALIFIED HUMAN RESOURCES ON ACCESS AND QUALITY OF HEALTH CARE IN BASIC HEALTH CENTERS

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ABSTRACT

The health system in developing countries, including Madagascar, is characterized by insufficient resources, including qualified human resources. This shortage is more noticeable in remote areas and makes access to primary care very difficult for the rural population. How does the imbalance in human resources present itself in the provision of primary care? This study analyzes the situation of primary health care in the Analamanga and Bongolava regions, focusing on the optimization of human resources in Basic Health Centers (CSB) and the prospects for strengthening essential services. The hypothesis put forward to answer the question raised is that the quality of health care provided in Basic Health Centres depends on the availability of qualified human resources, particularly doctors. Using quantitative data analysis, the correlations between various variables qualifying the quality of healthcare at CSB level and the availability of human resources were examined. The results highlight higher concentrations of healthcare professionals in urban versus rural areas, underlining potential challenges in terms of healthcare accessibility. Despite strengths in the distribution of human resources, limitations in data collection and quality were identified. This study provides a solid foundation for guiding policies and interventions aimed at improving primary healthcare in Madagascar, highlighting the importance of a holistic approach to strengthening both access and quality of primary healthcare.

Key words: *Primary healthcare, Human resources, Accessibility, Quality of care*

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the Alma Ata Declaration in 1978, the global vision of achieving health for all by the year 2000 through the promotion of primary health care has been a constant aspiration. In 1987, African countries reaffirmed this commitment by launching the Bamako Initiative, aimed at eliminating barriers and facilitating equitable access to healthcare for the entire population. A crucial element in achieving this goal is the availability and efficiency of resources in the healthcare system, thus guaranteeing the provision of equitable, quality care. From this perspective, access to primary health care is intimately linked to a number of factors, including the existence of adequate health infrastructures, with medical equipment and supplies, and the continued presence of qualified personnel (Meessen & Damme, 2005). Indeed, the availability and geographical distribution of health professionals play a decisive role in the accessibility and quality of basic health care (Graham et al., 2001). In Madagascar, national health policy involves user participation in the purchase of medicines, while the administration is responsible for building health infrastructure and recruiting health professionals (MSANP, 2016).

However, despite these efforts, the country faces a persistent shortage of qualified healthcare personnel, particularly doctors (Jacquemot, 2020). This shortage is exacerbated by the uneven distribution of medical human resources across Madagascar. Facing this contradictory realities, how can the poor population access quality primary care? This problematic defines the main objective: to analyze this dynamic in order to shed light on the challenges facing the Malagasy healthcare system and to identify avenues for better human resource management in the healthcare sector, with a view to improving primary healthcare for the entire population. The research question is: What is the impact of the availability of qualified human resources on access to and quality of healthcare in Basic Health Center noted "Centre de Santé de Base" (CSBs) in Madagascar? The hypothesis defines that the quality of healthcare provided in CSBs depends on the availability of qualified human resources, particularly doctors.

2. PRESENTATION OF THE STUDY AREA AND DATA COLLECTION

The healthcare system in the Analamanga (18.914871° S, Longitude 47.531612° E) and Bongolava (Latitude 18.500000° S, Longitude 46.099998° E) regions is a crucial aspect of the well-being of the inhabitants of these regions. To understand the current state of the healthcare system, it is essential to examine data concerning the types of CSB in Districts, Communes, and Fokontany corresponding to the administrative divisions of Madagascar. These data, sourced from the Ministry of Public Health database, also encompass their respective contexts and operating environments. The CSB's level is defined by the presence of a doctor: level 1 without a doctor, and level 2 with a doctor.

In the Analamanga region, which includes districts such as Antananarivo Renivohitra, Ambohidratrimo, Andramasina, Manjakandriana, Antananarivo Avaradrano, Anjozorobe, Ankazobe, and Antananarivo Atsimondrano, as well as several communes and fokontany, the health system is diverse in terms of urban and rural locations.

In districts such as Antananarivo Renivohitra and Antananarivo Avaradrano, which include many urban communes and fokontany, a concentration of CSB 2 is noted. These centers, located in urban areas such as *Ambalavao Isotry*, *Antohomadinika Afovoany*, and *Anosipatrana Atsinanana*, play a vital role in providing primary care to an often dense and diverse population. CSB1 are also present, although in smaller numbers, in fokontany such as Andraisoro and Anjoma Faliarivo. Districts such as Ambohidratrimo, Andramasina, Manjakandriana, Anjozorobe, Ankazobe, and Antananarivo Atsimondrano include rural areas. CSB 1 and CSB 2 are distributed across fokontany such as Ambato, Ambohitrandriamanitra, Beronono, and Analaroa. These health centers are often the main source of primary health care for remote rural communities, providing essential services such as vaccinations, prenatal care and basic medical consultations.

In the Bongolava region, which includes districts such as Fenoarivobe and Tsiroanomandidy, the health system reflects a dissimilar distribution between urban and rural areas. CSB 2 are present in urban fokontany such as Amparihibe and Ambohimandroso Bemasoandro, while rural communes such as Bevato, Ambatolampy, and Ankadinondry rely on CSB 1 and CSB 2 to meet the health needs of the population.

3. METHODS

To achieve this objective, a methodological approach based on geospatial analyses was used to examine the relationships between the availability of qualified human resources, the number of patients per healthcare professional, and the geographic accessibility of CSBs, and their impact on the quality of healthcare.

3.1 Geospatial analysis of healthcare professionals

Geospatial analysis is an essential component of this study, enabling an in-depth understanding of the distribution of qualified human resources in (CSB) in Madagascar. For this analysis, data were obtained from the Human Resources Department (DRH) of the Ministry of Public Health (MSANP) and processed using Geographic Information System (GIS) software, in this case ArcGIS.

The main objective of this cartographic analysis is to evaluate the distribution of CSBs in relation to established standards for the availability of healthcare professionals. The standards used as a reference were defined by national health authorities, taking into account various factors such as population density, local health needs and available resources.

Using available geographical data, each CSB was georeferenced and mapped according to its exact location. Next, a spatial analysis was carried out to assess the proximity of (CSBs) to areas with the highest demand for healthcare services, as well as their geographical distribution in relation to established norms. The results of this analysis

were used to identify areas where the availability of healthcare professionals was adequate, and those where gaps existed.

3.2 Intercorrelation of variables affecting health service quality

A correlation between different relevant variables was carried out in order to better understand the factors influencing the quality of health services in (CSB). Variables taken into account in this analysis include environment (urban or rural), public health standards, sector population in 2017, distance to District Health Offices (BSD), presence and qualification of the Chef de Poste, type of (CSB), regions, districts and communes, as well as availability of health personnel.

Using appropriate statistical techniques, such as Pearson correlation analysis, relationships between these variables were explored. This intercorrelation analysis enables to identify the main determinants of the quality of health services in (CSB), which in turn guides recommendations for optimizing human resources and improving access to quality health care in the regions studied.

4. FINDS

4.1 Availability of health professionals in Basic Health Centres

4.1.1 Geospatial analysis

The geospatial analysis of data concerning the availability of healthcare professionals in Basic Health Centres (CSB) provides a detailed overview of the distribution of these essential resources across different regions of Madagascar.

The results for each region studied in percentages are categorized according to several relevant variables such as environment (urban or rural), public health standards, and types of (CSB). Analysis of the data collected in the Analamanga and Bongolava regions of Madagascar reveals crucial information on public health infrastructure and the distribution of primary healthcare services across the different regions, districts and communes (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of healthcare professionals in the Analamanga and Bongolava regions

4.1.2 Repartition

The region is characterized by the presence of several CSB (Health Centers) spread across urban and rural areas. In urban areas such as Antananarivo-Renivohitra, a higher density of CSBs is observed, emphasizing essential medical services, including prenatal consultations and postnatal care. These centers, designed to effectively meet

the needs of the local population, are better structured and more prevalent in urban areas, where there are an average of 2 to 3 CSBs per commune.

CSBs come in different types, ranging from CSB1 to CSB2, each offering a specific range of services. The (CSB)₁, managed by at least one nurse or midwife, appear to focus primarily on providing a minimum package of primary care and information, while the (CSB)₂, managed by a doctor, offers a broader range of services, including medical consultations and nursing care.

The presence of a health post chief and health worker in most CSBs reflects a relatively well-organized infrastructure in terms of human resources. However, disparities persist in some areas where the presence of medical personnel is limited.

Analysis of the distance separating CSBs from the population they serve highlighted significant variations. While some CSBs are easily accessible to a large portion of the population, others were remote, posing barriers to accessing health care.

The quality of a CSB is often determined by its ability to meet the health needs of the local population. Standards of medical and nursing services fluctuated depending on the type of CSB and its location. However, it is imperative to ensure that each (CSB) scrupulously respects the minimum standards in order to ensure the provision of quality health services that are equitably distributed throughout the territory.

Figure 2: Characteristic of perceptions by each observation class at CSB level

4.1.3 Distribution by region and setting

The results reveal a marked predominance of rural areas in the majority of the regions studied. Of the 268 (CSB) examined, a significant proportion, 89.5%, are located in rural areas, while only 10.4% are located in urban areas. This distribution highlights the need to adapt staffing strategies according to the specific characteristics of each setting. The results show an uneven distribution in terms of compliance with standards between the two types of (CSB). In (CSB) 1, 72.6% of establishments are in compliance with established standards, while only 27.3% do not meet these standards. In contrast, in (CSB) 2, the situation is reversed, with 72% of establishments not meeting the standards and only 27.9% in compliance. Examining the distribution of (CSB) compliant with standards by region, significant variations are observed. For example, the Antananarivo-Renivohitra region stands out with

94.4% of its CSBs in compliance, while other districts such as Andramasina and Anjozorobe have lower levels, with 54.1% and 60% compliance, respectively. This observation suggests regional disparities in the availability of human resources and underscores the need for a more equitable allocation of health professionals (Figure 2).

4.1.3.1 Compliance with public health standards:

Examining the compliance of CSBs with established standards reveals that the availability of health professionals varies considerably from one region to another. For example, in some districts such as Antananarivo-Renivohitra, 100% of CSBs meet established standards, while in others, such as Andramasina, only 54.1% of CSBs are in compliance. This disparity highlights the need to review staffing strategies to ensure an equitable distribution of medical resources across the country (Figure 2).

• Impact of different types of (CSB):

Further analysis also reveals significant variations in the availability of healthcare professionals by type of (CSB). For example, (CSB) 1 generally have lower levels of availability compared to (CSB) 2. This observation underscores the importance of taking the diversity of healthcare facilities into account in human resource planning (Figure 2).

4.1.3.2 Impact of the post head and paramedic qualifications:

A more detailed analysis also reveals the significant impact of the post head and paramedic qualifications on compliance with standards. CSBs with a paramedic post head generally show higher levels of compliance compared to those without one (Figure 2).

The results on compliance with medical staffing standards provided valuable insights into the significant disparities between different regions and types of CSBs. These results provide valuable insights for developing more effective and equitable human resource policies aimed at ensuring equal access to quality health services across Madagascar. By taking into account regional specificities and the characteristics specific to each type of CSB, it becomes possible to implement targeted interventions to optimize human resource allocation and thus strengthen the health system as a whole.

4.2 Intercorrelation of variables qualifying the quality of health care at the CSB level and the availability of human resources

The regions studied have a dense network of CSBs, essential for providing primary health care to the population. Data analysis revealed several significant trends that can inform efforts to improve the quality of health services in the region.

First, it is important to note that geographic variables such as identification number, region, and district are highly correlated, highlighting the importance of considering geographic structure in health service planning.

Regarding the composition and availability of medical personnel, significant correlations with the type of CSB are observed. For example, CSB 2, which offers a wider range of services, is associated with a greater presence of doctors (correlation of 0.64) and state-registered nurses (correlation of 0.27). This suggests that the CSBs are better equipped with human resources to meet the population's health needs.

Furthermore, the distance between the CSBs and the district health offices also showed significant correlations with the availability of medical personnel. CSBs located further from the district health offices tend to have fewer doctors, raising concerns about the accessibility of health services in these remote CSBs.

Furthermore, population density in the areas where CSBs are located is a determining factor in the availability of medical personnel. CSBs located in densely populated areas tend to have more doctors, nurses, and midwives, reflecting the need to allocate human resources according to the demand for health services.

Table 1. Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variables	Num	Régions	Districts	Type CSB	Head of Post	MDE	IDE	SF	distance BSD	pop ^o Secto 2017	nbre AS /CSB	Norme	Milieu
Num	1,00												
Régions	0,65	1,00											
Districts	0,99	0,67	1,00										
Type CSB	-0,05	-0,03	-0,04	1,00									
Head of Post	-0,05	-0,03	-0,05	0,64	1,00								
MDE	-0,22	-0,17	-0,22	0,02	0,00	1,00							
IDE	-0,20	-0,11	-0,20	0,27	0,24	0,29	1,00						
SF	-0,07	-0,12	-0,08	0,12	0,18	0,56	0,11	1,00					
distance BSD	0,39	0,40	0,39	-0,18	-0,26	-0,23	-0,17	-0,19	1,00				
pop ^o Secto 2017	-0,24	-0,05	-0,25	0,26	0,30	0,65	0,42	0,31	-0,25	1,00			
nbre AS /CSB	-0,19	-0,17	-0,19	0,36	0,48	0,79	0,45	0,68	-0,35	0,67	1,00		

Norme	-0,08	-0,13	-0,09	0,26	0,46	0,45	0,35	0,47	-0,30	0,46	0,76	1,00	
Milieu	-0,31	-0,09	-0,31	0,10	0,20	0,43	0,33	0,20	-0,29	0,54	0,44	0,30	1,00

Values in bold are different from 0 at significance level $\alpha=0.05$

- The variables "Num", "Regions", and "Districts" are highly correlated with each other, which is expected since they represent geographic subdivisions (0.65; 0.99; 0.67).
- A significant correlation is observed between "Type (CSB)" and variables related to medical staff (MDE, IDE, SF), indicating that the type of health center influences the presence and distribution of medical staff (0.02; 0.27; 0.12).
- The "BSD distance" is negatively correlated with the presence of medical staff (MDE, IDE, SF) and compliance with health service standards, suggesting that (CSBs) located far from district health offices may be less well-equipped with human resources and less compliant with standards (-0.23; -0.17; -0.19).
- The "2017 Sect. Pop." is positively correlated with the presence of medical personnel (MDE, IDE, SF), meaning that (CSB) located in densely populated areas tend to have more medical personnel (0.65; 0.42; 0.31).
- The "Number of AS /(CSB)" is strongly correlated with the presence of medical personnel (MDE, IDE, SF), suggesting that health centers with a greater number of health workers per (CSB) also have a greater presence of medical personnel (0.79; 0.45; 0.68).
- The coefficients of determination show that the variables related to medical personnel (MDE, IDE, SF) have relatively weak correlations with the other variables, with the exception of "Type (CSB)" and the "2017 Sect. Pop."
- The "BSD distance" and the "Norm" have relatively low coefficients of determination with the other variables, which indicates that their variation is less explained by the other variables of the study (-0.30).

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Optimizing Human Resources in Basic Health Centers: Toward Strategies to Improve Access and Quality of Healthcare

Optimizing human resources in Basic Health Centers (BHCs) is critically important to ensure equitable access and quality healthcare for the population (Saint-Arnaud, 2003). The results highlight several significant trends that can guide the development of effective strategies in this area.

- It is crucial to recognize that BHCs, which offer a wider range of services, are associated with a greater presence of state-certified doctors and nurses (Elorza et al., 2016). Therefore, investing in the training and deployment of healthcare professionals in these BHCs can significantly improve the quality and diversity of services offered (Armstrong & Armstrong, 2002).

- The distance between (CSBs) and district health offices (DHOs) is a determining factor in the availability of medical personnel. (CSBs) located further from DHOs tend to suffer from a shortage of medical personnel (Campbell & Shojaei, 2018), which can compromise access to health care in these remote areas. Thus, targeted recruitment and retention strategies in these geographically remote areas are necessary to ensure adequate coverage of medical personnel (Alwan & Peter, 2002).

In addition, the data reveal that population density in the areas where (CSB) are located also influences the availability of medical staff. (CSBs) located in densely populated areas generally benefit from easier access to a qualified healthcare provider, underscoring the importance of taking local demographic variations into account when planning human resources.

Thus, to optimize human resources in CSBs, it is essential to implement strategies that are flexible and adapted to local needs. This could include outreach training and recruitment programs at (CSBs) (Benallah & Domin, 2017), financial incentives to attract healthcare professionals to remote areas (Chougrani & Ali, 2011), as well as initiatives to strengthen intersectoral collaboration for more holistic and effective health human resources planning. One of the main strengths of this study lies in its ability to provide practical and specific recommendations for optimizing human resources in (CSB). Using a rigorous analytical approach based on quantitative data, the study identifies significant trends concerning the availability and distribution of medical staff in (CSBs) of different categories.

By highlighting the association between the type of (CSB) and the presence of qualified health professionals, the study provides valuable guidance for strategic planning of health human resources (Kane et al., 2018). Furthermore, by examining the impact of geographical distance on the availability of medical personnel, the study highlights the importance of considering local factors in the design of health policies and programs.

By integrating these findings into a global analysis, the study offers practical recommendations for improving access to and quality of healthcare through targeted strategies such as strengthening the training and deployment of medical personnel (Organisation mondiale de la Santé, 2018), as well as providing financial incentives to attract healthcare professionals to remote areas (Kerouedan, 2009).

5.2 Perspectives for strengthening primary healthcare in Madagascar: Integrating the factors of availability and accessibility of health professionals

In Madagascar, strengthening primary health care (PHC) is essential for improving the health and well-being of the population, particularly in rural areas. The results provide valuable insights for integrating the factors of availability and accessibility of health professionals into strategies to strengthen PHC in the country (Dubois & Dussault, 2002).

It is imperative to recognize that the availability of medical personnel in (CSBs) is closely linked to the type of (CSB) and its geographical location (Harkat & Azzouzi, 2021). (CSB) 2s, which offer a wider range of services, are associated with a greater presence of state-qualified doctors and nurses (Amar & Abdelhak, 2017). Consequently, the expansion and strengthening of (CSBs) of this type can play a crucial role in improving access to PHC across the country.

The distance between (CSBs) and BSDs is a major challenge for the accessibility of healthcare services, particularly in remote areas (Dorier & Morand, 2012). To overcome this constraint, innovative solutions such as the deployment of mobile healthcare staff and teleconsultation can be explored to extend the reach of healthcare services in remote areas (Zidane & Lounes, 2019).

In addition, it is essential to take local demographic disparities into account when planning human resources for health. Densely populated areas generally benefit from better medical staff coverage, while less populated regions can suffer from staff shortages (Azzouzi & Acidi, 2017). Consequently, a differentiated approach tailored to local needs is required to ensure an equitable distribution of healthcare professionals across the country.

Integrating the factors of availability and accessibility of healthcare professionals into national strategies for strengthening PHC is essential for improving the health and well-being of the Malagasy population. By adopting a holistic, locally-focused approach (Charbonneau, 2018), Madagascar can move towards more effective and equitable PHC provision for all its citizens (Breton et al., 2011).

The strengths of this study lie in its ability to comprehensively address the challenges and opportunities associated with strengthening primary healthcare (PHC) in Madagascar. By focusing on integrating the factors of availability and accessibility of healthcare professionals (Okalla & Le Vigouroux, 2001), the study adopts a holistic approach that considers the multiple dimensions of the problem.

By identifying the links between the availability of medical personnel, the type of primary healthcare provider (PHC), and geographic location, the study offers a nuanced perspective on the challenges facing the Malagasy healthcare system. Furthermore, by exploring innovative solutions such as the deployment of mobile healthcare personnel and teleconsultation (Parizel et al., 2013), the study proposes concrete avenues for action to overcome barriers to healthcare accessibility in remote areas. Finally, by highlighting the importance of a differentiated approach based on local needs, the study highlights the need to adapt PHC strengthening strategies to the socio-demographic reality of Madagascar. By integrating these recommendations into a global perspective, the study offers a comprehensive framework for improving PHC delivery and promoting the health and well-being of the Malagasy population.

6. CONCLUSION

This study provided significant insights into the state of primary healthcare in Madagascar, with a particular focus on optimizing human resources in Basic Health Centers (BHCs) and opportunities to strengthen these essential services. The results of the quantitative analysis revealed interesting correlations between various variables characterizing the quality of healthcare at the BHC level and the availability of human resources. This intercorrelation underscores the importance of a holistic approach to improving both access to and quality of primary healthcare. The data also highlighted strengths in the distribution of human resources, including a higher concentration of health professionals in urban areas compared to rural areas. The stated hypothesis, "the quality of healthcare provided in BHCs depends on the availability of qualified human resources, particularly physicians," was confirmed.

However, several limitations were identified in the methodology and scope of the study. Limitations include gaps in data collection and quality, as well as potential biases related to study design and data analysis. Despite these limitations, this study provides a solid foundation for guiding policies and interventions aimed at improving primary health care in Madagascar. Strategies targeted at optimizing human resources, taking into account geographic disparities and the specific needs of the populations served, could help strengthen primary health services and improve long-term health outcomes. Finally, it is essential that the findings of this study be proactively used by policymakers, health practitioners, and health system stakeholders to inform concrete actions aimed at promoting effective, equitable, and accessible primary health care for all Malagasy citizens.

7. REFERENCES

- [1]. Alwan, A., & Peter, H. (2002). Les répercussions de la réforme du secteur de la santé sur le développement des ressources humaines. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 56–60.
- [2]. Amar, A., & Abdelhak, A. (2017). Les motifs des choix d'installation des médecins privés à Annaba. *Revue internationale de soins palliatifs*, 32(1), 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.3917/inka.171.0005>
- [3]. Armstrong, P., & Armstrong, H. (2002). *Planification des soins: Approches en matière de politiques et de planification des ressources humaines de la santé*. Commission sur l'avenir des soins de santé au Canada.
- [4]. Azzouzi, A., & Acidi, A. (2017). La répartition spatiale inégale des médecins privés en lien avec leurs motifs d'installation dans la wilaya d'Annaba. The unequal spatial distribution of private doctors in relation to their reasons for settlement in the province of Annaba. *Bulletin de la Société Royale des Sciences de Liège*. <https://doi.org/10.25518/0037-9565.7313>
- [5]. Benallah, S., & Domin, J.-P. (2017). Réforme de l'hôpital. Quels enjeux en termes de travail et de santé des personnels ? *La Revue de l'Ires*, 91–92(1–2), 155–183. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rldi.091.0155>
- [6]. Breton, M., Levesque, J.-F., Pineault, R., & Hogg, W. (2011). L'implantation du modèle des groupes de médecine de famille au Québec: Potentiel et limites pour l'accroissement de la performance des soins de santé primaires. *Pratiques et Organisation des Soins*, 42(2), 101–109. <https://doi.org/10.3917/pos.422.0101>
- [7]. Campbell, J., & Shojaei, T. (2018). Ressources humaines en santé dans les pays d'Afrique francophone: Dynamiques et défis: *Santé Publique, HS(HS)*, 5–5. <https://doi.org/10.3917/spub.180.0005>
- [8]. Charbonneau, G. (2018). Le recrutement de médecins pour la pratique en milieu rural. *Canadian Family Physician*, 64(8), 622–622.
- [9]. Chougrani, S., & Ali, A. D. (2011). Perception de la qualité des soins chez les professionnels de santé de l'Établissement Hospitalier et Universitaire d'Oran (EHUO). *Santé Publique*, 23(6), 475–485. <https://doi.org/10.3917/spub.116.0475>
- [10]. Dorier, E., & Morand, E. (2012). " Accessibilité aux services de soins en situation post conflit, République du Congo. *Bulletin de l'Association de géographes français*, 2012–2, pp 289.
- [11]. Dubois, C.-A., & Dussault, G. (2002). La politique de ressources humaines et la transformation des systèmes de soins. *Gestion*, 27(3), 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.3917/riges.273.0055>
- [12]. Elorza, M. E., Moscoso, N. S., & Lago, F. P. (2016). Accès potentiel aux ressources humaines de soins primaires dans la Province de Buenos Aires (Argentine). *Horizonte sanitario*, 15(3), 123–133.
- [13]. Graham, W. J., Bell, J. S., & Bullough, C. H. (2001). L'assistance qualifiée à la naissance peut-elle réduire la mortalité maternelle dans les pays en développement? *Réduire Les Risques de La Maternité: Stratégies et Évidence Scientifique*, 105–139.
- [14]. Harkat, M. L., & Azzouzi, A. (2021). La répartition spatiale des médecins privés à Annaba (est algérien). *Revue internationale de soins palliatifs*, 35(1), 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.3917/inka.211.0013>
- [15]. Jacquemot, P. P. (2020). *LES SYSTÈMES DE SANTÉ EN AFRIQUE MIS À L'ÉPREUVE*.
- [16]. Kane, H., Jabot, F., & Hsairi, M. (2018). Les ressources humaines en santé: Planification et parcours individuels: *Santé Publique, HS(HS)*, 7–8. <https://doi.org/10.3917/spub.180.0007>
- [17]. Kerouedan, D. (2009). De plus en plus de malades et de moins de soignants: La crise des ressources humaines du secteur de la santé en Afrique. *Journal Africain du Cancer / African Journal of Cancer*, 2(1), 115–122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12558-009-0022-3>
- [18]. Meessen, B., & Damme, W. V. (2005). Systèmes de santé des pays à faible revenu: Vers une révision des configurations institutionnelles ? *Mondes en développement*, 131(3), 59–73. <https://doi.org/10.3917/med.131.0059>
- [19]. MSANP. (2016). *PNS*.
- [20]. Okalla, R., & Le Vigouroux, A. (2001). Cameroun: De la réorientation des soins de santé primaires au plan national de développement sanitaire. *Bulletin de l'APAD*, 21, Article 21. <https://doi.org/10.4000/apad.181>
- [21]. Organisation mondiale de la Santé. (2018). *Directives de l'OMS sur la politique de santé et l'accompagnement au sein du système en vue d'optimiser les programmes relatifs aux agents de santé communautaires*. Organisation mondiale de la Santé. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/325564>
- [22]. Parizel, É., Marrel, P., & Wallstein, R. (2013). La télémédecine en questions. *Études*, 419(11), 461–472. <https://doi.org/10.3917/etu.4195.0461>
- [23]. Zidane, D., & Lounes, N. (2019). *La télé santé et les apports de la télé consultation dans la prise en charge des problèmes de santé publique: CAS DE LA COVID 19 AU CHU NEDIR MOHAMMED DE TIZI-OUZOU* [Université Mouloud Mammeri]. <https://dspace.ummtto.dz/handle/ummtto/16210>